

Measurement Report

Sample Name : 2

Measurement Date: 26.08.2025 13:38

by: ExpertName

Report Date: 26.08.2025 13:44

by: ExpertName

SOP : DefaultSOP

Solvent : Water

Refractive index : 1.331

Viscosity at 24.94 °C : 0.89 cP

Device : Amerigo

Wavelength : 638 nm

Laser power : 10 %

Temperature set by: None

Resolution : MEDIUM

Dielectric Constant: 78.08

Electrode Distance : 5 mm

Henry function : Smoluchowski

Experiment : Acquisition

Measurements per sequence: 6

Overview

Start Time (hh:mm:ss)	Carrier frequency(Hz)	Resistivity factor (V)	Applied field (V/cm)	Laser Power (%)
8/26/2025 1:38:19 PM	7996	5.624	20.3	10

	Mean	Std Dev
Mobility (µm.cm / V.s)	-3.94	0.13
Zeta Potential (mV)	-50.77	1.67

Measurement n°	Mobility (µm.cm / V.s)	Zeta (mV)
1	-4.17	-53.62
2	-3.79	-48.74
3	-3.98	-51.18
4	-3.79	-48.74
5	-3.98	-51.18
6	-3.98	-51.18

Start (hh:mm:ss) : 26.08.2025 13:38
T(°C) : 24.9°C Applied field (V/cm) : 20.3
Reference intensity (kcps) 32
Scattering intensity (kcps) 2556